

Comparison of classical, semiclassical and quantum methods in hydrogen broadening of
nitrogen lines

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ABSTRACT

We use an accurate *ab initio* potential energy surface (PES) in order to inter-compare various methods commonly employed to calculate pressure broadening coefficients. Close-coupling (CC) calculations of the collisional line widths of the isotropic Raman lines of N₂ perturbed by H₂ are performed for temperatures between 77 and 2000 K. The CC results compare well with available experimental values. Three less exact methods of calculation are also used: the full classical (FC) model of Gordon, the semiclassical (SC) formalism of Robert and Bonamy and the quantum dynamical Coupled States (CS) method. The CS method provides good agreement with CC calculations for all studied temperatures, FC calculations can be considered as accurate above room temperature while the SC method gives overestimated values by about 20 – 30 % in all cases. The temperature dependences of pressure broadening coefficients provided by each method are very similar at elevated (above room) temperatures.

Keywords : Collisional broadening, linewidths, pressure broadening, nitrogen, hydrogen, classical, semiclassical and quantum methods

1. Introduction

Molecular nitrogen (N_2) is one of the major components of atmospheric and combustion media. Several studies concerning collisional processes where N_2 is the active molecule have been carried out for both kinds of media [Lavorel86, Rahn86, Bonamy91, Gomez06, Gomez07]. For the atmospheric applications, the interest is mainly focused at low temperatures, contrarily to the high temperatures considered in the thermometry studies of combustion media, where N_2 is taken as a probe molecule for the determination of local temperature or concentration [Bohlin09, Bohlin10].

Experimental measurements of collisional broadening of the Raman Q-branch of the fundamental band of N_2 perturbed by H_2 were compared with semiclassical calculations in Ref. [Gomez06] and with quantum dynamical calculations in Ref. [Gomez07]. The analytical interaction potential used in the semiclassical ones corresponds to the addition of an electrostatic term and an atom-atom Lennard-Jones potential that takes into account the interaction at close intermolecular distances. In Ref. [Gomez06], the experimental measurements were obtained at 77 and 298 K. For room temperature a good agreement was found between experiments and calculations using a fitted value for the kinetic diameter of an atom-atom potential. Nevertheless, a discrepancy attributed to orbiting collisions, which are not taken into account in the semiclassical model of Robert and Bonamy (RB) [Robert79], was observed at 77 K. On the other hand, CC and CS dynamical calculation were performed on an *ab initio* potential energy surface (PES) [Gomez07, Gomez-PES, cappelletti08]. The resulting pressure broadening coefficients compare well with measured values between 77 and 580 K.

It has been argued that the CC and CS methods are too much time consuming and therefore alternative methods should be used [Buldyreva05, Nguyen06, Ivanov05]. As discussed in Ref. [Thibault11], this could be true 20 years ago, but not in the present days, when the computational facilities have improved considerably since then. Moreover, for diatom – diatom collisions with ortho and para species, as it is the case for the N_2 - H_2 system, this separation allows to speed up the calculations [Thibault08, Thibault09Cappelletti, Thibault09Fuller, Thibault11]. Moreover, when the PES is not too deep the construction of a grid of pressure broadening cross-sections at various kinetic energies is not useful and the approximation which consists in performing the calculation at the single kinetic energy associated with the mean thermal relative speed is justified, allowing an important economy

of CPU time. We will discuss these aspects in Section 2. However, at high temperatures a great number of rotational levels are populated ($j \geq 30$) and so the CC and CS methods become anyway heavy and the use of alternative methods is appropriate. Therefore this study is also of some interest for thermometry applications based on nitrogen CARS spectra [Bohlin09, Bohlin10].

In this work, we present a comparison between full classical (FC), semiclassical (SC)[†], and quantum dynamical (CC and CS) calculations of the collisional broadening of N₂ perturbed by H₂, but now, the same *ab initio* PES is used in all the cases in order to properly compare the different methods of calculation. We have considered the Raman Q-branch lines of N₂ in N₂-H₂ mixtures for a large range of temperatures (77 – 2000 K) and N₂ rotational quantum numbers ($j = 0 - 30$). This way, we can also determine the appropriate use of each method for each range of temperature. This work is therefore a continuation of our recent study [Thibault11] where we have dealt with the C₂H₂-H₂ system and where we concluded that: 1) the CS approximation and the full classical method of Gordon [Gordon66I, Gordon66II] implemented by Ivanov [Nguyen06, Ivanov05, Ivanov08, Ivanov10] lead to similar results above room T ; 2) the semiclassical method of Robert and Bonamy [Robert79] is unable to provide accurate results using an *ab initio* PES; 3) the temperature dependence of the PB coefficients is very similar for all methods considered, justifying the use of the RB method with effective potentials. And finally, because the PES of the present N₂-H₂ system is much less anisotropic (at least at short range) than that of C₂H₂-H₂ system we should obtain a better agreement using the RB method.

In section 2 very few dynamical details about the used PES are presented. We also discuss the ortho-H₂ and para-H₂ contributions to the total PB cross-sections and the utility of the thermal average operation. In section 3 we compare calculated and experimental values of the collisional broadening coefficients and their temperature dependence as well as the results of the different theoretical methods between them. Section 4 resumes the conclusions of this work.

2. Dynamical calculations

[†] Unless otherwise stated SC is equivalent to RB, the Robert-Bonamy semiclassical method; FC is the full classical method Gordon implemented by Ivanov (so called C3D method of Refs. [Gordon66I, Gordon66II])

The dynamical calculations were performed on the *ab initio* N₂-H₂ PES which is thoroughly discussed in Refs. [Gomez07, Gomez-PES, Cappelletti08]. Since one aim of the present work is to compare the methods of PB coefficients calculation, the four methods used here employed the same development over bispherical harmonics (the multipolar expansion) of the potential (see Eq. (8) of Ref. [Gomez07]). Therefore there is no *ad hoc* expression nor L_Jn_m fitted form of any component of the PES as this is usually the case with the RB formalism. Since the PES is only four dimensional our calculations are performed within the rigid rotor approximation.

Quantum dynamical calculations were done with the MOLSCAT code [Hutson95]. Since very similar calculations were recently reported [Thibault08, Thibault09Fuller, Thibault09Cappelletti, Thibault11, Gomez07] we only provide very few details. Due to the fact that what we are primarily calculating are two states-to-two states cross-sections $\sigma(j_A j_B \rightarrow j'_A j'_B)$, where j_A and j_B are the pre-collisional rotational quantum numbers of N₂ and H₂, we have performed two kinds of MOLSCAT runs. One kind for ortho-nitrogen interacting with para-H₂ (pH₂) molecules and one kind for oN₂ interacting with ortho-H₂ (oH₂) molecules. This is due to the fact that the interactions are unable to convert an oH₂ molecule to a pH₂ molecule and conversely. Note that we have only performed such calculations for even nitrogen rotational j quantum numbers (oN₂). With the close-coupling method we have calculated such cross-sections for oN₂-pH₂ over a grid of 127 total energies between 15 and 1600 cm⁻¹ and for oN₂-oH₂ over a grid of 115 total energies between 136 and 1500 cm⁻¹. With the coupled-states method we build a grid of 86 energies between 13 and 3400 cm⁻¹ for oN₂-pH₂ collisions and a grid of 82 energies between 133 and 4000 cm⁻¹.

At a detailed level, one can define a kinetic energy dependent partial PB cross-section as:

$$\sigma(j_A, j_B; E_{kin}) = \sum_{j'_A \neq j_A, j'_B} \sigma(j_A j_B \rightarrow j'_A j'_B; E_{kin}) \quad (1)$$

from which a thermally averaged PB cross-sections $\sigma(j_A, j_B; T)$ can be obtained assuming a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, at a given temperature T , of the kinetic energies E_{kin} . For even rotational perturber states this allows to define a para (partial) PB cross-section

$$\sigma_{pH_2}(j_A; T) = \sum_{j_B \text{ even}} \rho_{j_B}(T) \sigma(j_A, j_B; T) \quad (2)$$

and for odd rotational perturber states:

$$\sigma_{oH_2}(j_A; T) = \sum_{j_B \text{ odd}} \rho_{j_B}(T) \sigma(j_A, j_B; T) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\sigma(j_A, j_B; T) = \frac{1}{(k_B T)^2} \int \sigma(j_A, j_B; E_{kin}) E_{kin} \exp(-E_{kin} / k_B T) dE_{kin} . \quad (4)$$

Therefore the total PB cross-section (in \AA^2) in natural- H_2 for a $Q(j_A)$ line is given by:

$$\sigma(j_A; T) = \frac{1}{4} \sigma_{pH_2}(j_A; T) + \frac{3}{4} \sigma_{oH_2}(j_A; T) \quad (5)$$

and the corresponding PB coefficient (in $10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$) by:

$$\gamma(j_A) = \frac{56.6915}{\sqrt{\mu T}} \times \sigma(j_A; T) . \quad (6)$$

In the above equations ρ stands for the H_2 populations and μ for the reduced mass ($\mu=1.87 \text{ u}$).

Fig. 1. Selected N_2 - H_2 partial pressure broadening cross-sections $\sigma(j_A j_B; E_{kin})$ (see Eq. (1)) as a function of the kinetic energy. Top for $j_A=0$, bottom for $j_A=10$; solid line for $j_B=0$, long dash for $j_B=1$, medium dash for $j_B=2$ and short dash for $j_B=3$.

Figure 1 shows the variation with the kinetic energy of partial cross-sections for $j_A = 0$ and $j_A = 10$. We observe in each case that the cross-sections for the different j_B are different at low kinetic energy but converge to the same value as the kinetic energy increases. We also note that the partial PB cross-section for $j_B = 0$ is the smallest one and that this effect is more pronounced for $j_A = 0$ than for $j_A = 10$. This overall behavior was also noticed for the $C_2H_2-H_2$ system (see Fig. 3 of Ref. [Thibault08]) and an explanation was provided. However, for the present system the convergence is faster with the kinetic energy, this should be due to the smaller anisotropy of the PES.

These results can be summarized by looking at the ortho and para partial PB cross sections at various temperatures. Figure 2 presents such cross-sections at 77 and 298 K. We see that while at 77 K it is still important to distinguish between the H_2 species at room T it is no longer necessary. Therefore at higher T one can avoid the calculations of one kind of such partial cross-sections [Thibault08, Thibault09Fuller] and, moreover, after careful check, perform the calculation for only one j_B value (fig. 1). Obviously, such findings may be also important for FC calculations.

The important CPU time required by quantum dynamical methods as compared to the RB method has been often invoked to justify semiclassical calculations[‡]. For the N_2-H_2 system, as this is the case for $C_2H_2-H_2$ [Thibault11] and all systems involving a linear molecule and the hydrogen molecule quantum dynamical calculations are not so time consuming. Nevertheless, still with the objective to economize CPU time we address the question of the necessity or not of the thermal average. This quadrature operation (Eq. (4)) is often skipped for technical reasons using the RB method. Within this approximation, for a

given temperature T , calculations are performed at the kinetic energy $\frac{4}{\pi}k_B T / hc$ (263.5 cm^{-1} at 298K for instance) associated with the mean relative speed $\bar{v} = \sqrt{\frac{8k_B T}{\pi\mu}}$. Figure 3 compares thermally averaged and not thermally averaged PB coefficients at 77 and 298 K obtained with the CC scheme. At 77 K relative differences as large as 20% are observed but at room T the maximum relative difference is no more than about 4%. Since the kinetic energy dependent PB cross-sections become smooth and nearly constant (Fig. 1) at high energy,

[‡]For instance for oN_2-pH_2 the CPU time required on an Intel Xeon dual core 2.66 GHz was respectively for the CC and CS methods: 9.7 s and 3.4 s at a total energy of 262 cm^{-1} ; 166 min and 2 min 4s at a total energy of 1000 cm^{-1} .

there is no significant difference between thermally averaged and unaveraged PB coefficients for temperatures above room T . Obviously, the same observations are made using the CS and FC methods. These results justify, *a posteriori*, the fact that in Ref. [Gomez07] unaveraged PB coefficients, above room temperature, were compared with experimental values and the fact that in the present study we did not perform the thermal average for the SC calculations. Note that because the potential well depth is smaller for the present system than that for $C_2H_2-H_2$ one this approximation is valid at a lower T for N_2 in H_2 [Thibault11].

Finally, note that for CC calculations we have completed our CC grid by CS calculations (this is justified in the next section by the intercomparison) in order to perform the thermal average. This grid was completed by 2×8 additional CS calculations, from 1700 to 3400 cm^{-1} for oN_2-pH_2 and from 1600 to 4000 cm^{-1} for oN_2-oH_2 . In addition, our quantum dynamical pressure broadening cross-sections were extrapolated up to 5500 cm^{-1} with a simple functional dependence: $\sigma(E_{kin}) = a + b/E_{kin}$ [DePristo79], where a and b are constants. Therefore unaveraged CC values are available up to 1500 K; at the highest temperature investigated, 2000 K, our quantum dynamical unaveraged values are only CS values.

Fig. 2. Comparisons of thermally averaged (top at 77 and bottom at 298 K) ortho- H_2 and para- H_2 contributions to the total (CC) PB cross-sections for various $j=j_A$ N_2 rotational quantum numbers.

Fig. 3. Comparison at 77 K (for the CC method only) and 298 K (for the CC, CS and FC methods) between thermally averaged (filled symbols) and unaveraged (open symbols) N_2 PB coefficients.

3. Comparisons and discussions

In order to estimate the quality of the results obtained by the different methods, we have compared them with the experimental results of Refs. [Gomez06, Gomez07]. In figure 4 we have represented the broadening coefficients obtained from the four methods considered here: CC, CS, FC and SC, and the cited experimental ones, at four different temperatures: 77, 298, 440 and 580 K. For all these temperatures, we observe a very good agreement between CC, CS and experimental values, specially taking into account the error bars. Results of the FC method are about 30% higher than experimental ones for 77 K, and less than about 10 % for 298 K. For 440 K this method gives the values within the error bars but a little bit higher than experimental ones. For 580 K we find a very good agreement with experience using the FC method. Now considering the results provided by the RB method, we must note that the SC values are always overestimated by about 20-30 % for all the temperatures.

Since CC is the most exact method and it provides calculated values in very good agreement with measurement, we can consider them as benchmark data for the other methods, allowing comparing the four methods for a wider range of temperatures, up to 2000 K. This is done in Fig. 5. For all the cases the CS approximation gives almost the same

results as the CC method, with only a little difference of some percents. As expected, at 173 K the agreement using the FC method is better than at 77 K. Calculations performed at 1000, 1500 and 2000 K confirm that both CS and FC methods ensure correct predictions above room T. Note that the CC/CS pressure broadening coefficients are less accurate as j increases due to the large spacing of our grid in energy at high energies. Typical uncertainties are about 3% for $j=10$ and 5% for $j=24$.

Fig. 4. (a)–(d), comparisons between experimental [4,5] N_2 PB coefficients (\times , with their error bars) and full classical (down triangles), semiclassical (up triangles: filled RB-PT, open RB-ET), coupled states (squares) and close-coupling (circles) calculated values. Note that the CC values, as the temperature increases, are nearly indistinguishable at the scale of the figure from the CS values. In (a) the dashed line represents extrapolated values (for even j values) from the use of Eq. (7) and Table 1. In full classical calculations Monte Carlo RMS error is generally maintained less than 1% for all j and T . (a) $T=77$ K, (b) $T=298$ K, (c) $T=440$ K and (d) $T=580$ K.

Fig. 5. Comparisons of full classical (down triangles), semi-classical (up triangles: filled RB-PT and open RB-ET), coupled states (squares) and close coupling (circles) PB coefficients of N_2 in H_2 at various temperatures ((a)–(d)). All the reported values are unaveraged ones. Circles when they are not observed are under the squares. In (d), the dashed line represents extrapolated values obtained through Eq. (7) and Table 1. (a) $T=173 \text{ K}$, (b) $T=1000 \text{ K}$, (c) $T=1500 \text{ K}$ and (d) $T=2000 \text{ K}$.

Finally, figure 5 shows that SC results are considerably too large for all the temperatures, presenting values about 20 – 30 % higher than those from CC in all the cases, even for the highest temperatures, for which this method is expected to be more accurate on the basis of a classical translational motion. Unfortunately, this is exactly the high temperature domain which necessitates alternative methods to quantum ones.

In Ref. [Joubert08], the CC and CS broadening coefficients of Ref. [Gomez07] are used to obtain an Energy Corrected Sudden scaling law (ECS) giving the cross-sections of N₂ – H₂ system. The parameters of the scaling law were fitted to find a good agreement with the only thenadays available CC and CS values, which correspond to temperatures between 77 and 580 K. Then, this law was used to extrapolate the values of the PB coefficients to higher temperatures until 2000 K. In Ref. [Bohlin09], PB coefficients for N₂ – H₂ system are taken into account for fuel rich hydrocarbon flames thermometry of N₂. ECS parameters of Ref. [Joubert08] are used in [Bohlin09] to obtain the PB coefficients for N₂ – H₂. If we compare our presently calculated CC/CS values at 2000 K with the extrapolated ECS values obtained in [Joubert08] or [Bohlin09], at the same T , we can observe that the latter are underestimated by about 20 %. The present results indicate clearly that the conclusion of Bohlin et al [Bohlin09] which emphasizes “the importance of using adequate Raman line widths for accurate rotational CARS thermometry” may be biased. It is clear that to obtain correct ECS values new CC values calculated in the present work must be taken into account in the fitting of the ECS parameters. This would be useful if temperatures above 2000 K are required. Nevertheless, to interpolate PB coefficients between 77 and 2000 K a simple semi-empirical law is used in the following paragraph. Experimental thermometry measurements of [Bohlin09], as well as those of Ref. [Bohlin10] (where experimental measurements are compared with RB values of PB coefficients as [Bohlin09]) can now be directly compared with mcurrent calculations.

As mentioned above, to interpolate our results, we have also studied the temperature dependence of the PB coefficients. We have considered the following semi-empirical law:

$$\gamma(T) = \gamma(T_{ref}) \left(\frac{T_{ref}}{T} \right)^n. \quad (7)$$

In this expression, T_{ref} is a temperature of reference that usually corresponds with the room temperature. In figure 6, we plot the temperature exponents n derived from considered 4 computational methods versus the rotational quantum number j . We have calculated these coefficients for two different temperature ranges: $T < 298$ K and $T > 298$ K. Use of the CC, CS or the SC method does not lead to significant differences (<5%) for these exponents in the 2 ranges (reported values in figure 6 are averaged values for 11 different temperatures between 77 and 2000 K). For the FC method the reported values were obtained for temperatures greater than the room T (at lower T the obtained exponent are about 10% larger). Once more, CC and CS calculations present similar results. The RB method gives the same kind of temperature dependence as CC or CS, with n values differing of former ones in

about -10 % in the worst case, taking into account results for $j \leq 16$. Table 1 provides CC thermally averaged values with the n exponent determined over the full range of temperature. Test of use of Eq. 7 are shown (by dashed lines) at 77 K in figure 4 and at 2000 K in figure 5.

Fig. 6. Exponent for the temperature dependence of the N_2 PB coefficients (Eq. (7)) from full classical (down triangles), semi-classical (up triangles), coupled states (squares) and close coupling (circles) calculations.

Table 1
Thermally averaged CC pressure broadening coefficients (in $10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$) at 298 K and exponent n for the use of Eq. (7).

j	γ	n
0	63.75	0.49
2	47.40	0.43
4	49.65	0.47
6	50.70	0.47
8	51.10	0.48
10	50.70	0.47
12	50.10	0.46
14	49.35	0.45
16	48.45	0.44
18	46.90	0.42
20	45.20	0.40
22	43.35	0.39
24	40.80	0.37
26	39.05	0.35
28	40.15	0.36
30	35.90	0.33

The temperature dependence of the PB coefficients is quite good as shown here and in Ref. [Thibault11]. This is why, as discussed in Ref. [Thibault11] and observed in Refs. [Afzelius04, Lambot91, Bouanich02, Ivanov08, Buldyreva04, Buldyreva06], the parameters of analytical effective potential currently used in the RB method can be adjusted to well reproduce experimental values, and then interpolate between them or extrapolate in a given range of temperatures. This is of practical interest when complex molecules are considered and more exact methods become too time consuming. Nevertheless, this method does not provide good results when an *ab initio* potential is used in its original form [Thibault01,

Buldyreva05, Nguyen06, Ivanov05, Ivanov10, Afzelius04]. This is attributed partly to the fact that the RB approach neglects the exchanges between translational and rotational degrees of freedom.

Fig. 7. Comparison at various temperatures of full classical PB coefficients of N_2 in H_2 determined with trajectories driven by the full potential (filled symbols) or by the isotropic component of the potential only (open symbols).

As previously [Thibault11], trying to understand the defect of the RB method we have performed some additional FC calculations in which the trajectory is simply guided by the isotropic component of the PES, as it is the case in all semiclassical methods applied to the line broadening mechanism [see references therein Nguyen06, Ivanov05, Ivanov08, Ivanov10]. Looking at figure 7 leads us to a few observations. First, use of “isotropic” trajectory generally overestimates the PB coefficients as this is the case for the RB values as compared to other methods. Second, such approach does not improve as T increases, as discussed in [Thibault11]. Third, this approximation gets better in the present N_2 - H_2 case as compared to C_2H_2 - H_2 system. This was expected [Thibault11] on the basis that the PES of the N_2 - H_2 system is more isotropic. Moreover, since the rotational constant of nitrogen ($\sim 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is greater than the rotational constant of the acetylene ($\sim 1.17 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) rotational-translational exchanges should be weaker in the former case lowering the defect of the SC formalism. Such considerations explains why the PB coefficients obtained using the RB method are globally in better agreement with values obtained using the other methods in the present case as compared to what is observed in [Thibault11]. This is particularly true at room T .

Similar conclusions were obtained in Ref. [Thibault11] where the more complex $C_2H_2 - H_2$ system has been studied. Due to the anisotropy introduced for acetylene at short range and the lightness of the perturber, this system is not the more appropriate to study from the semiclassical point of view. However, we could expect more realistic results for the $N_2 - H_2$

system, but once more, this is not the case. In fact, because the rotational constants of such molecules are very different, the energy levels of the interacting pair are far from resonance and the validity of any semi-classical approximation is questionable. The RB formalism has been too widely used, because people have forgotten the limits of the method, which were, however, well known by the founders. This is due to the fact that the Robert–Bonamy method [Robert79] is simple to implement and not time consuming due to its analytical treatment. Thanks to this virtue it was easily extended to more involved situations [Buldyreva11, Hartmann08].

4. Conclusion

In this work, starting with the same N₂–H₂ ab initio PES, we have compared the PB coefficients of N₂ Raman lines provided from quantum dynamical (CC, CS), full classical and semiclassical methods over an extensive range of temperatures (77–2000 K). We have first noticed that ortho- and para-H₂ contributions to the N₂ linewidth above the room T are very comparable. In addition, we have observed that for temperatures above 298 K thermal average is not required. Both observations give the route to speed up the calculations without loss of accuracy. The close-coupling method is the most exact one and is in good agreement with experience as showed in Ref. [Gomez07]. The coupled states approximation is in a very good agreement with CC for all the studied temperatures. The CS method is found here more accurate than for C₂H₂–H₂ (see Ref. [Thibault11]) because of greater isotropy of the N₂–H₂ PES and weaker long range forces [Gomez07]. The full classical method of Gordon is, on the overall above the room T, accurate and gives a good temperature dependence of PB coefficients for T > 298 K. The semiclassical framework of Robert–Bonamy gives values overestimated by up to 20–30% even for the highest temperatures considered, for which it was considered to be more appropriate for the present system as compared to the C₂H₂–H₂ system. However, the RB method shows a good temperature dependence of the pressure broadening coefficients, and so it can be used in conjunction with effective potentials to interpolate or extrapolate such coefficients in a limited range of temperature. The next challenge will be to perform the same intercomparison with a more suitable system for any semi-classical method. A C₂H₂–N₂ ab initio potential energy surface has been recently calculated for this purpose.

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